

On the effective potential of photons near Schwarzschild-type black holes in Starobinsky-Bel-Robinson gravity

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Abstract

The theoretical modelling of black holes (BHs) in diverse space-time frames with modified gravity provides a semantic way to understand the distinct physical scenarios of black holes present in the universe. Here, we have studied the effective potential for the photon in the vicinity of recently framed Schwarzschild-type black holes (SBHs) in Starobinsky-Bel-Robinson (SBR) gravity. We have deduced the trajectory defining the effective potential from the Lagrangian. The expression of effective potential has two extended terms due to the implementation of superstring type-2 theory. Furthermore, there is no effective potential for the radial motion of photons. It has been noted that the shape and size of an effective potential plot for non-radial motion depend upon the combination of both l and α .

Keywords— Black hole, Starobinsky-Bel-Robinson gravity, Superstring type-2 theory, Effective potential

1 Introduction

The arduous study of Black holes (BHs) has exhilarated many physicists and mathematicians for many years. Prior research has extensively investigated the theoretical frameworks of BHs to manifest the idea of properties of physical BHs. The study of BHs has also been prominently researched due to its application in explaining the properties of space-time. One of the well-known ways to understand the structure of space-time is to study the geodesic trajectories of particles.

To explain the cosmological observations, different perturbed gravity models are taken into consideration in studying BHs. The concept of understanding the motion of freely moving particles near BHs with modified gravity involves numerical techniques to solve nonlinear geodesic equations. In literature, BHs are extensively studied with the modified gravity like $f(R)$ gravity [1, 8, 9, 11, 26, 32, 39], Einstein-Maxwell-dilaton gravity [13, 36, 38], Hořava-Lifshitz gravity [4, 7, 21, 23], conformal gravity and its perturbed forms [16, 17, 20, 24, 25, 28, 29], Einstein-Weyl gravity [15, 22, 41, 42], mimetic gravity [3, 14, 30, 31, 33–35, 40] etc to reveal their nature.

The quadratic extension of Ricci scalar, R , in Einstein gravity enumerated with 11D M-theory or superstring type-2 theory deduces the expression for action in Starobinsky-Bel-Robinson (S-B-R) gravity [18]. The quantum correction and coupling constant correction in the Starobinsky model of inflation provided further perception on the model of gravity [19, 37]. Furthermore, Ruben et al. [12] defined BHs in the Schwarzschild metric for S-B-R gravity and computed its entropy, temperature, lifetime and pressure. The optical properties, shadows, tidal effect and gravitational lensing for SBHs in S-B-R gravity are then explored by Belhaj et al. [2, 5], Arora et al. [2] and Mushtaq et al. [27], whereas the quasinormal modes and its correspondence with null geodesics were recently explained by Bolokhov [6]. Moreover, Davlataliev et al. [10] studied the trajectories of magnetized and charged particles in the surroundings of SBHs in S-B-R gravity.

Bolokhov [6] deduced the null geodesics for SBHs in S-B-R gravity. Whereas, the presented paper further analyzes the effective potential for massless particles in the vicinity of SBHs in SBR gravity.

The following paper is carried as: section 2 introduces the spacetime model of BHs in SBR gravity. Further in the following section, the effective potential near focused BHs is derived for photons with the consideration of their rotational and non-rotational motion. Lastly, we concluded the study in section 4.

2 Theoretical modeling

The expression of a line element can be obtained by extremizing the action and applying boundary conditions for a BH. Here, the 4- dimensional action integral in superstring type-2 theory is provided as, [18]

$$S = \frac{M_{pl}}{2} \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \left(R + \frac{R^2}{6m^2} - \frac{\alpha}{32m^6} (P_4^2 - E_4^2) \right) \quad (1)$$

The line element for the Schwarzschild BHs following the above action is given by, [12]

$$ds^2 = -Z(r)dt^2 + \frac{1}{Z(r)}dr^2 + r^2d\lambda^2 \quad (2)$$

Where, $\lambda = d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\Phi^2$, and $Z(r)$, metric function is defined as,

$$Z(r) = 1 - \frac{2M}{r} + \frac{p\alpha M^9}{r^9} - \frac{q\alpha M^{10}}{r^{10}} \quad (3)$$

p , q and α in above expression are dimensionless real constants with values, $p = 968392.8$, $q = 1739520.4$ and $0 \leq \alpha \leq 3.9 \times 10^{-6}$. The term α is known as coupling constant enumerated from the superstring type-2 theory. [37]

3 Effective potential for null geodesics

The effective potential for the line element (2) can be deduced from the Langrangian defined as,

$$L = \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} \dot{x}^\mu \dot{x}^\nu$$

Figure 1: Variation of effective potential, $V(r)$, with respect to r for $l^2 = 10$ where, (a) $\alpha = 0.1$, (b) shows for $\alpha = 0.001$ (yellow), $\alpha = 0.002$ (cyan) and (c) $\alpha = 0.0001$.

After enumerating the metric function in above equation, the Langrangian for the motion of photon in equatorial plane ($\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$) can be expressed as,

$$2L = - \left\{ 1 - \frac{2M}{r} + \frac{p\alpha M^9}{r^9} - \frac{q\alpha M^{10}}{r^{10}} \right\} \dot{t}^2 + \left\{ 1 - \frac{2M}{r} + \frac{p\alpha M^9}{r^9} - \frac{q\alpha M^{10}}{r^{10}} \right\}^{-1} \dot{r}^2 + r^2 \dot{\Phi}^2 \quad (4)$$

The constant of motion from equation (4) is founded to be,

$$E = Z(r)\dot{t} \quad (5)$$

$$l = r^2 \dot{\Phi} \quad (6)$$

Using the equations, (5) and (6) in Constraint equation, $g_{\mu\nu}\dot{x}^\mu\dot{x}^\nu = 0$, we get the effective potential as,

$$V(r) = l^2 \left\{ \frac{1}{r^2} - \frac{2M}{r^3} + \frac{p\alpha M^9}{r^{11}} - \frac{q\alpha M^{10}}{r^{12}} \right\} \quad (7)$$

3.1 Radial motion

By implementing the condition of radial motion, $l = 0$, of photon in the vicinity of Schwarzschild BHs in S-B-R gravity, we get no influence of effective potential on the particle. Since,

$$V(r) = 0 \quad (8)$$

Figure 2: Variation of effective potential, $V(r)$, with respect to r for $l^2 = 10$ where, (a) shows the variation for different values of α , green for $\alpha = 10^{-2}$, yellow for $\alpha = 10^{-3}$, cyan for $\alpha = 2 \times 10^{-3}$, purple for $\alpha = 10^{-6}$ and red for Schwarzschild BHs (b) shows the plot for certain region of r .

Figure 3: Variation of effective potential, $V(r)$, with respect to r for different values of l , $l^2 = 10$ (yellow), $l^2 = 15$ (red), $l^2 = 20$ (green), $l^2 = 30$ (blue) where, (a) for $\alpha = 0.1$ and (b) for $\alpha = 10^{-6}$.

3.2 Non-radial motion

The value of effective potential will be same as deduced in equation, (7) and figure shows the variation of effective potential, $V(r)$ with respect to r for different values of l .

4 Conclusion

In this study, we have evaluated the trajectory defining effective potential (7) for the motion of massless particles at the proximity of Schwarzschild-type BHs in SBR gravity. It can be noted that the effective potential has two extended terms due to the implementation of superstring type-2 theory in the Starobinsky inflation model of gravity. For the photons moving radially, the effective potential is reduced to zero (8), similar to Schwarzschild BHs in Einstein gravity. Hence, these photons will directly fall into the singularity without facing any potential barrier. Whereas, for non-radial motion, fig(1) and fig(2) shows that the shape of the graph of $V(r)$ vs r depends upon the value coupling constant, α . Even the small variation in the value of α can alter the shape to great extent as shown in fig(1b). The roots of $V(r)$ also came out to be dependent on the value of α , fig(2b). The trajectory

of these photons will therefore depend upon the parameter α . Fig(2a) shows the effective potential compared to Schwarzschild BHs in Einstein gravity. It can be observed that the solution defined for Schwarzschild BHs in SBR gravity approaches the solutions in Einstein gravity as α approaches zero. Further, it is perceived from the fig(3) that the angular momentum l does not affect the shape of effective potential plots but changes its size.

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